

Validated index of green and blue space quality

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Executive Summary

Green and blue spaces, in urban and rural locations, are vital to the health of our communities, economies, and environment. Encouraging, managing, and investing in outdoor access has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to health, planning, environment, education, and tourism. To understand the quality of publicly available green and blue spaces in Scotland we initially undertook a scoping review, identifying 68 quality indicators that are currently used in Scotland, or similar locations (Roberts et al., 2023a). Here, we extended this research through an online survey and workshops with stakeholders from across Scotland to meet six objectives:

Objective One: Identify any indicators missing from the literature review, either in current use or aspirational in Scotland.

Four new indicators not found through the scoping review (Roberts et al., 2023a) were identified through the survey, giving a final list of 72 potential quality indicators for green and blue space in Scotland. These four indicators include:

- Drought susceptibility
- Food growing opportunities
- Invasive species
- Renewable energy generation

Objective Two: Categorise quality indicators according to importance, including consideration of green and blue space types and for whom;

The most important indicators of both green and blue space quality were identified as:

- Accessibility - getting there
- Accessibility - for those with a disability
- Accessibility - proximity
- Aesthetics - generic
- Biodiversity species diversity
- Biodiversity - species richness
- Presence of protected plants/animals
- Regulation of ecological quality
- Water quality - generic

Additionally, in green spaces only accessibility – generic, physical health, pollination potential, presence of wildlife, and protected status were also identified as of high importance. In blue spaces, aesthetics, carbon storage, drought susceptibility, and invasive species were additionally of high importance.

Objective Three: Understand bundles of, or trade-offs between:

- quality indicators
- green and blue space quality

Five green space bundles and eight blue space bundles were recognised. Accessibility related indicators were the indicators most often in opposition to other bundles. This trade-off will need careful consideration in management.

Objective Four: Identify the policies to which quality indicators may be relevant, and how or where they may impact.

Environmental and socio-economic policies (at international, national, and local levels) were most often linked to the quality indicators. In total 91 policies were identified as being relevant to green and blue space quality measurement, and 62 out of the 72 indicators were connected to policies.

Objective Five: Identify barriers to measuring quality indicators and to embedding quality indicators in policy.

Seven barriers were identified including those for:

- Use of indicators
 - Complex methods
 - Poorly defined indicators
- Embedding indicators into policy
 - Public perception
 - Short policy cycles
 - Policy coherence
- Cross cutting
 - Knowledge, skills, and capacity
 - Data availability

Objective Six: Identify potential impacts of the indicators.

The potential impacts of indicators included:

- Improved quality of outdoor space
- Community resilience and empowerment
- Health and wellbeing
- Local economy
- Improved monitoring
- Targeted interventions
- Engagement with the public
- Improved environmental outcomes

Next steps

The indicators prioritised here will be taken forward to create a validated toolkit for estimating the costs and benefits of green and blue space management, accounting for specific uses and underrepresented groups. In the final year of the project this toolkit will be applied to rural and urban case studies.

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1. Introduction

Green and blue spaces, in urban and rural locations, are vital to the health of our communities, economies, and environment. Their contributions to health and wellbeing mean that increasing access to the outdoors is a Scottish Government National Performance Framework indicator. Encouraging, managing, and investing in outdoor access has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to health, planning, environment, education, and tourism. However, conceptualising green and blue spaces as uniform in their capacity to deliver benefits does not account for variation in their quality (i.e., their ability to deliver benefits). Recent work on the benefits of urban green space has identified quality as of more importance than quantity (Dobson et al., 2019). Despite ongoing interest in the characterisation of the quality of green and blue spaces, definitions and indicators of green and blue space quality are seldom consistent. Understanding how quality of green and blue spaces is measured in relation to the multifunctionality of these spaces will therefore contribute to improving management, policy, and decision making to produce better outcomes, for both people and the environment.

Green and blue spaces provide benefits across environment and society. The “Four Capitals” approach provides a lens through which to conceptualise these benefits, and has been applied by the Scottish Government in relation to post-Covid recovery (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020). The Four Capitals are defined as:

- Environment – Natural Capital: nature’s stock of natural assets.
- People – Human Dimension: health, skills, and knowledge accumulated by individuals.
- Community – Social Capital: shared understandings that enable cooperation.
- Business – Economic Capital: products of human productive activities.

We have applied this lens to understanding the benefits from green and blue space, although noting that differentiation between each capital may not be clear cut in all cases (i.e., some services may arguably be placed in multiple capitals). In this report we consider publicly accessible green (e.g., public parks, forests) and blue (e.g., coastal waters, rivers). Although private green and blue spaces can provide complimentary services to those provided by public spaces (Hanson et al., 2021), they are not under the control of public bodies, and therefore opportunities for influencing management is limited.

We initially undertook a scoping review to identify the types of green and blue space quality indicators that are currently used in Scotland, or similar locations (Roberts et al., 2023a). In that assessment of the literature, we identified 68 indicators of green and blue space quality. The majority of these indicators related to the “environment” and “people” categories within the Four Capitals framework, with only six indicators of quality for the community, and five for quality for business. The indicator codebook, which provides a description of each quality indicator, split by category, can be found in Appendix A.

Here, we extended this research through an online survey and workshops with stakeholders from across Scotland to meet six objectives:

1. Identify any indicators missing from the literature review, either in current use or aspirational in Scotland;
2. Categorise quality indicators according to importance, including consideration of green and blue space types and for whom;

3. Understand bundles of, or trade-offs between:
 - a. quality indicators
 - b. green and blue space quality
4. Identify the policies to which quality indicators may be relevant, and how or where they may impact;
5. Identify barriers to measuring quality indicators and to embedding quality indicators in policy; and,
6. Identify potential impacts of the indicators.

2. Methods

This current research is built on the 68 indicators identified through our scoping review on green and blue space quality in Scotland (Roberts et al., 2023a). The research reviewed 83 papers analysing green and blue space quality across Northwest Europe. A list of the 68 indicators identified and their definitions can be found in the codebook in Appendix A.

2.1 Survey

We carried out an online survey to address objectives 1 (identify missing indicators) and 2 (categorise importance of indicators). A link to the survey was sent directly to green and blue space policymakers, managers, and community and business users, along with a request to send the link to other colleagues and contacts who may have an interest in green or blue space quality (Table 1).

Table 1 Stakeholder types

Stakeholder type	Reason for invite
National policy	Understand where green and blue space fits in national level policy decision making.
Local policy	Understand where green and blue space fits in local level policy making.
Green/blue space managers	Knowledge of current quality indicators and practicality of carrying it out in different types of green/blue space
Green/blue space business users	Knowledge of green/blue space users and needs. Experience of trade-offs.
Green/blue space community groups	Knowledge of green/blue space users and needs. Experience of trade-offs.
Nature-based health intervention organisers	Knowledge of green/blue space users and needs – particularly those working with hard-to-reach groups.

The survey first asked for details of the type of stakeholder, the categories of green and blue space, and specific users of the space the individual worked with. These questions included open text boxes to expand on multiple choice answers where relevant. Participants were then presented with a list of the previously identified 68 indicators (Roberts et al., 2023a) and asked to identify which they used, or would be interested to use. They were invited to add in any indicators that they use in their

own work not already listed. Finally, of the indicators that they use, or would like to use, participants were asked to identify the degree of importance as “most important”, “important”, “least important”. “Importance” was defined here as importance for their role in their category of green and or blue space.

To make the parsing of the 68 indicators easier, indicators were presented in coherent groups, based on the Four Capitals, with the question repeated between each group. A default choice of “I do not use this indicator” was selected in the first instance to reduce cognitive burden on participants.

2.1.1 Survey analysis

To understand importance, we first calculated the mean and median scores for each indicator, creating a ranked score of indicators. These rankings were further refined in the workshops. To enable focus in the workshops on the indicators for which importance was less clear, we also calculated the variance for each of the indicators. Higher variance indicates lower agreement between scores, and therefore an indicator which would benefit from further exploration in the workshops. All analyses were carried out in R v4.1.3 (R Core Team, 2022).

2.2 Workshops

We carried out two workshops to address objectives 2 (categorise importance of indicators), 3 (understand bundles and trade-offs), 4 (identify policies), 5 (identify barriers), and 6 (identify potential impacts). To facilitate involvement of stakeholders from different geographical areas to attend, we held the same workshop in two locations, Perth and Aberdeen, Scotland. The workshops lasted from 10am until 3:30pm. The workshop invitation was circulated to the same stakeholders to whom we sent the survey.

The workshop consisted of five different activities to address the five objectives. Information from the survey was used specifically for activity 1 exploring indicator importance. Additionally, the updated list of indicators, with the addition of the 4 new indicators that were identified in the survey (see section 3.2), was relevant to all the activities. Participants were sent the list of indicators (72 in total) and their description in advance of the workshop. These descriptions can be found in the codebook for the 72 indicators in Appendix A. The analysis of each of the activities is set out within the activity detail.

2.2.1 Activity 1: Indicator importance ranking

This activity addressed objective 2 (categorise importance of indicators).

In this activity participants refined the ranking of the indicators from the survey. Participants were provided with the 28 indicators where the degree of importance was less clear; these were clustered based on the mean ranking from the survey (Least important, Important, Most important). The four new indicators identified through the survey were unranked. Using two different coloured sticky dots – one to specify increasing importance, the other decreasing importance – participants were asked to individually place a sticky dot against any of the 28 indicators to be adjusted in the level of importance. For each of the new indicators, participants indicated them as very important, important or not important. This process was done for both green space and for blue space.

These ranking were then deliberated. Where there was consensus over shift in ranking, the indicator was placed in the new ranking.

For the analysis, we added these findings to that of the survey to produce the rankings of the 72 indicators. Any discrepancies between green and blue space were recorded.

2.2.2 Activity 2: Bundles and trade-offs concept maps

This activity addressed objective 3 (understand bundles and trade-offs).

In this activity the participants created concept maps with the 72 indicators drawing arrows to show the positive and negative relationships between the different indicators. Two concept maps were created in each workshop, one considering blue space and one considering green space.

Each of the workshops produced two concept maps (one green space, one blue space), resulting in four total. Concept maps were digitized using Miro, and then converted into matrices on Microsoft Excel (Appendix B). These matrices show both the direction of relationships and the value of relationships (i.e., positive, whereby increasing the level of one indicator increase the level of that indicator it shares the relationship with, or negative, whereby increasing the level of one indicator decreases the level of that indicator it shared the relationship with). Once converted to matrices, R v4.1.3 (R Core Team, 2022) was used to compare similarities and differences between the concept maps from each workshop (Perth green space vs. Aberdeen green space, and Perth blue space vs. Aberdeen blue space). Where there were differences between the maps from different workshops the following were decided:

- If one group of participants had said there was not a connection between indicators, but another group of participants had said there was, the connection was taken from the group that said there was one. This was to allow for all possible connections to be recorded.
- If one group had said a relationship was unidirectional and another that it was bidirectional, the bidirectional relationship was used in final analysis. This was done on the basis that a bidirectional relationship represents two relationships.
- Where there were differences on positivity or negativity of the relationships the research team discussed and came to a decision based on their knowledge of the indicators. There were some occasions when one workshop group had given both positive and negative values to a relationship, and these were also discussed by the research team. In instances where it was decided that relationships could be both positive and negative, the relationships were removed from further R analysis.

Assessment of these differences led to the merging of matrices, leaving two matrices: one for Green Space, and one for Blue Space. Where there were conflicting relationship values between concept maps of the same space either one value was chosen by the research team based on their understanding of the topic or, in the cases where relationships could be both positive and negative, the values were removed from analysis. See Appendix C for more details.

The two resulting matrixes were analysed using R v4.1.3 (R Core Team, 2022). Results showed the indicators for Green and Blue Spaces that had the highest numbers of indicators feeding into them. Indicators were then split into two groups: one for place-focused indicators, and one for person-focused indicators. See Appendix B for more details.

2.2.3 Activity 3: Policies

This activity addressed objective 4 (identify policies).

In this activity the participants identified policies for which the indicators were relevant and then connected specific indicators to these policies. Either large post-it notes were used to record the policies identified, or they were written directly on flipchart paper, then smaller post-it notes were used for participants to write down indicators and place these next to the appropriate policy.

For the analysis, a matrix was created with the appropriate policies and indicators in Microsoft Excel to analyse the relationships. For each policy, the following were identified to explore the reasons behind the relationships with the indicators:

- The year the policy was published.
- The policy mechanism, i.e. whether it was a steering strategy, instrument, or primary legislation ¹.
- The topic area of the policy, such as environment and socio-economic. A full list is provided in the results.

2.2.4 Activity 4: Barriers

This activity addressed objective 5 (identify barriers).

In this activity the participants identified barriers to both measuring quality indicators and embedding indicators into policy. The participants wrote these on post-its and these were stuck to two different boards, one for barriers to measuring quality indicators, the other for barriers to embedding indicators into policy. These post-its were then clustered together with participants into themes.

For the analysis, the themes and post-its were reviewed for commonalities and differences, and coded to produce the outputs in the barriers' results section (3.6) below.

2.2.5 Activity 5: Impacts

This activity addressed objective 6 (identify potential impacts).

In this activity the participants identified the impact of improving quality indicators on three aspects: wider society, their work, and the green and blue spaces themselves. They did this in three separate stations focusing on the three aspects of impact. The information was recorded on flip chart paper.

For the analysis, the outputs were thematically analysed to produce the results in the impacts section (3.7) below.

For further information on the workshop activities please see the workshop protocol (Roberts et al., 2023b).

^{1 1} We define steering strategies as non-binding policy that sets out the government (local or national) approach. This includes discussion papers, strategies, programmes, frameworks, reports, and plans. We define instruments as techniques or tools used by government to achieve certain objectives. These can include regulation, funding scheme, formal guidance and advice. We define primary legislation as legal policy. This could include legislation, statement [when summarising content of legislation or policy], or consultation [on proposed legislation].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 General

3.1.1 Survey

The survey ran from 3rd to 31st July 2023, and received 51 responses from an initial email list of 198. Given that we requested participants to forward the email invite to others in similar positions, a final response rate cannot be calculated. Of the 51 responses 40 were complete and taken forward for analysis. Participant roles were predominantly local level policymakers; few business owners took part (Table 2). Urban and rural spaces were evenly represented, with both coastal and islands also represented in smaller numbers. While over 80% of participants selected public parks and gardens, green corridors and natural and semi-natural, all types of space were selected by at least 30% of participants. All habitat types were also well represented, with grasslands, woodlands, and wetlands the most common (Table 3). Nearly all participants considered the general population as their user group. The most common specified group was people with a disability, followed by age related groups (Table 4).

Table 2 Participant role in green and/or blue space

Role	Percentage
Local level policy	63%
Green/blue space manager	33%
Nature-based Intervention	25%
National level policy	23%
Community group	15%
Business owner – direct use	3%
Business owner – indirect use	0%

Table 3 Type of green and/or blue spaces participants work in

Location type	Percentage	Habitat	Percentage
Urban	75%	Grassland	93%
Rural	75%	Woodland	85%
Coastal	48%	Wetland	80%
Island	20%	Urban	73%
Type of space		Heathland and scrub	65%
Public park/garden	88%	Coastal water including beaches	50%
Natural/semi-natural	85%	Lochs	50%
Green corridor	83%	Rivers or canals	50%
Amenity space	78%	Sparsely vegetated	50%
Children’s playspace	63%	Marsh inlets and transitional waters	28%
Blue space	53%	Cropland	23%
School or institutional ground	53%		
Civic space	43%		
Sports area	33%		
Burial ground	30%		

Table 4 General population participants worked with in green and/or blue spaces

Population	Percentage
General	95%
People with a disability	43%

Children (0-11)	38%
Young People (12-18)	35%
Older people (65+)	33%
Women	25%
Men	23%
People from Black or Minority Ethnic group	20%
Members of the LGBTQ+ community	18%
People with a specific religion	10%

3.1.2 Workshop

In total, there were 19 attendees, 14 in the Perth-based workshop and five in the Aberdeen-based workshop. Of these, 10 work in national policy, seven work in local policy, one is a nature-based intervention organiser, and one is a green/blue space business user.

3.2 Objective one: Identify any indicators missing from the literature review, either in current use or aspirational

Four novel indicators were identified through the survey:

- Food growing opportunities
- Drought susceptibility
- Invasive species
- Renewable energy generation

These were derived from 25 proposed by survey participants (Appendix D). Of these, 14 were determined by the research team to fit within existing indicators, and five were either not considered to be indicators of green space quality, or were not specific enough to be understood by the project team. The new 'invasive species' combined native and non-native invasive species into one indicator. The definition of these indicators can be found in the codebook in Appendix A.

3.3 Objective two: Categorise quality indicators according to importance, including consideration of green and blue space types and for whom

To understand indicator importance, we first asked survey participants about their indicator use. The most commonly used indicator was green/blue space size, followed by presence of protected plants and animals (Table 5). Carbon storage had the highest number of participants wanting to use the indicator, although only four participants reported currently using the indicator. Regulation of ecological quality, soil conservation, financial benefits, and tourism potential were also indicators with high numbers of participants wanting to use the indicator. Indicators which were most frequently used were largely indicators of environmental quality, with the addition of two indicators for accessibility. Indicators that participants wanted to use were spread more evenly across the Four Capitals categories, including environment, business, and people. The indicators which were not often used were also drawn from indicators of quality for the environment, for people and for business (Table 5).

Table 5 Indicator use

I use this indicator	I want to use this indicator	I do not use and have no interest in this indicator
Environment indicators		
Biodiversity – generic Diversity of terrain Ecological connectivity (e.g., connection to other green/blue spaces) Green/blue space size Naturalness Physical structure Presence of protected plants/animals Presence of wildlife Protected status of the green/blue space Vegetation cover	Air pollution Biodiversity – species diversity Biodiversity species abundance Biodiversity species richness Carbon storage Integration with landscape Pollination potential Presence of water Regulation of ecological quality Size and number of trees Soil conservation Water quality generic	Allergenic potential NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index, remote sensing) Noise pollution Temperature Water flow and discharge Water quality - disease causing bacteria Water quality nutrient
People indicators		
Accessibility generic Accessibility – proximity (e.g., close to the community)	Accessibility – barriers Accessibility – getting there Accessibility – internal Accessibility for those with a disability Activities Aesthetics – generic Aesthetics – maintenance Aesthetics – vegetation Aesthetics – view Connection to nature Duration of time spent in green/blue space Education/learning potential Frequency of visits Indices of multiple deprivation Mental wellbeing Physical activity promotion Physical health Quietness Recreation facilities Safety Services – generic Spiritual wellbeing Uniqueness	Incivilities (e.g., unwanted graffiti) Services people (non-recreational services) Sports facilities
Community indicators		

	Cultural sites Historical sites Services – community Social interaction	Children's playspaces Spiritual sites
Business indicators		
	Financial benefits Flood risk Tourism potential	House prices Services - business

Indicators colour coded by Four Capitals Framework and listed in alphabetical order. For indicator definitions please see the indicator codebook in Appendix A.

3.3.1 Indicator importance

Survey participants rated the importance of indicators they either used, or wanted to use. Indicators which had high agreement on their importance (variance under 1.4) were placed into the importance categories indicated by the survey responses (non-italic indicators in Table 6). Those indicators which had high variance were further explored within the workshops (italicised indicators in Table 6). The results examine indicator importance overall, as well as for in green and blue spaces.

Nine indicators were identified as “most important” across both green and blue spaces (Table 6). Additionally, there were five indicators “most important” in green spaces but not blue spaces, and five in blue spaces but not green spaces (Table 6). Ten of the indicators had different rankings between workshops. Where this occurred, the first approach was to follow the method of the survey, and average the ranking, (i.e., those that had been ranked as both most important and least important were ranked as important); where this was not possible, we chose the higher ranking. The indicators where this occurred are denoted by an asterisk in the table and further detail can be found in Appendix E.

Of the “most important” indicators, five are related to environmental quality, including three specifically related to biodiversity. The remaining indicators were categorised as quality for people, with three specifically related to accessibility. All the indicators of quality for businesses were found in the “least important” category, suggesting that this aspect of quality is less significant for the stakeholder types involved in the workshops (Table 6). Business owners were underrepresented in our survey, and only one was present at either of the workshops.

The indicators recognised as “most important” in the green spaces only are also environmental and people related indicators, with the two people related indicators linked to direct use of the area (physical health and accessibility – generic). In the blue spaces, the only people-related indicator is aesthetics, likely due to there being more passive uses of blue space than green space.

There is an overall mismatch between the indicators that were identified as most often used, and those that were identified as most important. Only ‘presence of protected plants and animals’ and ‘accessibility – proximity’ were present in both high use and high importance. This suggests that indicators currently in use may not always be most suited to measuring the important elements of green and blue space quality. Five of the indicators identified as “most important” were also identified as “want to use” indicators (regulation of ecological quality, biodiversity – species diversity, water quality – generic, accessibility for those with a disability, biodiversity – species

richness), as was carbon storage, which was identified as “most important” in blue spaces. Developing agreed metrics for these indicators may therefore have the largest impact on improving understanding of green and blue space quality.

Table 6 Indicator importance ranked through the survey and workshop separated by indicator category.

Most important	Important	Least important
Environment indicators		
<i>Biodiversity – species diversity</i> <i>Biodiversity – species richness</i> <i>Presence of protected plants/animals</i> <i>Regulation of ecological quality</i> <i>Water quality – generic</i> <i>Pollination potential (G)</i> <i>Protected status of the green/blue space (G)</i> <i>Carbon storage* (B)</i> <i>Drought susceptibility * (B)</i> <i>Presence of wildlife * (G)</i>	Biodiversity – species abundance Diversity of terrain Green/blue space size Naturalness Physical structure Presence of water Size and number of trees <i>Ecological connectivity (inc. edge diversity index)</i> <i>Vegetation cover</i> <i>Integration with landscape*</i> <i>Pollination potential (B)</i> <i>Protected status of the green/blue space (B)</i> <i>Biodiversity – generic* (G)</i> <i>Carbon storage* (G)</i> <i>Drought susceptibility * (G)</i> <i>Presence of wildlife * (B)</i>	Air pollution Allergenic potential NDVI Noise pollution Soil conservation Temperature Water flow and discharge Water quality – disease causing bacteria Water quality – nutrient <i>Biodiversity – generic* (B)</i>
People indicators		
<i>Accessibility – for those with a disability</i> <i>Accessibility – getting there</i> <i>Accessibility – proximity</i> <i>Aesthetics - generic</i> <i>Accessibility generic (G)</i> <i>Physical health (G)</i> <i>Aesthetic – Maintenance, well kept, management, cleanliness * (B)</i> <i>Invasive species * (B)</i>	Aesthetics – Vegetation Aesthetics – View Duration of time spent in green/blue space Education/learning potential Frequency of visits to green/blue space Physical activity Quietness Services – community Services – generic Spiritual wellbeing	Activities Incivilities Recreation facilities Services people Sports facilities Uniqueness <i>Safety (G)</i>

	<i>Accessibility – barriers</i> <i>Accessibility – internal</i> <i>Connection to nature</i> <i>Mental wellbeing</i> <i>Food growing opportunities*</i> <i>Indexes of multiple deprivation</i> <i>in which the site sits*</i> <i>Accessibility generic (B)</i> <i>Physical health (B)</i> <i>Safety (B)</i> <i>Aesthetic – Maintenance, well kept, management, cleanliness</i> <i>* (G)</i> <i>Invasive species * (G)</i>	
Community indicators		
	<i>Social interaction*</i>	Children’s playspaces Cultural sites Historical sites Spiritual sites
Business indicators		
<i>Flood risk (B)</i>	<i>Renewable energy generation*</i> <i>Flood risk (G)</i>	Financial benefits House prices Services – business Tourism potential

Indicators in italics had high variation in the survey findings and so were included in the workshop

Indicators colour coded by Four Capitals Framework

* This indicator had uncertainty in its categorization from the workshop, see Appendix B for further information.

(G) denotes ranking for green space consideration only.

(B) denotes ranking for blue space consideration only.

For indicator definitions please see the indicator codebook in Appendix A

3.4 Objective three: Understand bundles or trade-offs between quality indicators, as well as between green and blue space quality

3.4.1 Bundles

From the concept maps (Appendix F – I) five green space bundles (Figure 1) and eight blue space bundles (Figure 2) were identified. These bundles were created from the green and blue space indicators that had the highest number of relationships to other indicators, and therefore the increase in quality of one indicator will lead to an increase in the bundled indicators. Indicators that feed into multiple bundles may be particularly important to measure, as they may be more useful for inferring information about a number of different indicators at once. For example, the indicator *Soil conservation* feeds into all five of the top Green Space bundles. This means that participants

believed an increase in levels of *Soil conservation* would also mean an increase in levels of the title indicators of each of the bundles. Indicators that are present in multiple bundles may be more valuable to measure if resources are limited as they address multiple bundles at once. Having so many indicators appearing in more than one bundle suggests that participants – who work with green and blue space quality measures – see strong linkages between the indicators put forwards to them as part of this work.

Figure 1 Green Space Bundles. These bundles are indicators that had the highest number of relationships with others at the workshops. Below each of these main indicators (bold) are the indicators that feed into them via a positive relationship. The number next to the indicators is the total number of green space bundles that the indicators feed into. Participants recorded the majority of these relationships as strong, but some were considered weaker. These weaker relationships are shown with the addition of an asterisk (*) The indicator category is represented by the colour: Environmental, People, Community, Business.

Figure 2 Blue Space Bundles. These bundles are indicators that had the highest number of relationships with others at the workshops. Below each of these main indicators (bold) are the indicators that feed into them via a positive relationship. The number next to the indicators is the total number of blue space bundles that the indicators feed into. The indicator category is represented by the colour: Environmental, People, Community, Business.

3.4.2 Trade-offs

Some of the bundles of indicators also had negative relations to other quality indicators (i.e., as the quality of one indicator increased, the quality of the other decreased) (Table 7 and Table 8). Most but not all bundles had associated trade-offs, some with multiple indicators. The most common indicators included in trade-offs are those regarding accessibility, trading off with biodiversity in green spaces and protected area, size, protected plants and animals and financial benefits in blue spaces. Given that access to green and blue spaces is often an important aspect of their purpose, particularly in urban areas, this trade-off with other quality indicators should be carefully considered in management.

Table 7 Green space trade-offs.

Green space bundle	Trade-offs
Size and number of trees	None
Education/Learning potential	None
Presence of wildlife	None
Ecological connectivity	Carbon storage Invasive species
Biodiversity – generic	Accessibility – getting there Water quality – disease causing bacteria Aesthetics – maintenance (*)

* indicates a weaker relationship. The indicator category is represented by the colour: Environmental, People, Community, Business.

Table 8 Blue space trade-offs.

Blue space bundle	Trade-offs
Education/Learning potential	None
Biodiversity – generic	Duration of time spent in Green/blue space Food growing opportunities
Protected area	Duration of time spent in green/blue space Accessibility – generic Accessibility - internal
Green/blue space area	Accessibility – internal
Protected plants/animals	Accessibility – generic Water quality – disease causing bacteria Frequency of visits to green/blue space Accessibility – proximity Connection to nature Invasive species
Biodiversity – species diversity	Water quality – nutrient Noise pollution
Financial benefits	Accessibility – getting there Flood risk
Uniqueness	Pollination potential

* indicates a weaker relationship. The indicator category is represented by the colour: Environmental, People, Community, Business.

3.5 Objective four: Identify the policies to which quality indicators may be relevant, and how or where they may impact

In total there were 91 policies identified by the participants of both the workshops. Five of these were international, two of them were UK level, 52 were national to Scotland, 24 of them were local level policies and eight were unclear. Over half of the policies (54) were steering strategies, 16 were instruments, 11 were primary legislations, one was a partnership between different organisations, and nine were unclear². The unclear result came from where policies were mentioned in the workshop without sufficient clarification, and it was therefore not possible to be sure what policy was being referred to. Clarification was sought from the participants after the workshop where possible. Sixty-two of the 72 quality indicators were identified as being relevant to one or more of these policies.

Additionally, the policies were split by broad topic. Overall, 9 policy topic areas were identified. Where policies cover multiple topics, the primary topic was selected as the identifier. The number of policies for each topic can be viewed in Table 9. The largest topic was environment, which is perhaps unsurprising as the focus is on green and blue space. The second largest topic was socio-economic, which is also as expected, partly because this covers a large range of subtopics, but also because the focus of our research is on the quality of green and blue space for human use.

Table 9 Number of policies per policy topic

Policy topic area	Number of policies
Environment	35
Socio-economic	28
Climate change	9
Health	7
Transport	4
Housing	3
Energy	2
Land	2
Agriculture	1

The analysis suggests that whilst quality indicators may be relevant for many environmental policies, they are particularly important for socio-economic and health related policies as well. The 10 policies with the highest number of indicators linked to them are visible in Table 10. The top five of the nine policy topic areas are represented within the top 10 policies, with the distribution being broadly similar to the distribution in the whole sample. Three policies are environmental policies, two are socio-economic, two are health, one climate change and one transport. However, interestingly, the most common policy topic area, environment, is not present in the top five policies in Table 10 and policies that are more focused on people (socio-economic, health, and transport) seem to dominate in those top five policies.

² We define steering strategies as non-binding policy that sets out the government (local or national) approach. This includes discussion papers, strategies, programmes, frameworks, reports, and plans. We define instruments as techniques or tools used by government to achieve certain objectives. These can include regulation, funding scheme, formal guidance and advice. We define primary legislation as legal policy. This could include legislation, statement [when summarising content of legislation or policy], or consultation [on proposed legislation].

Table 10 Policies by the number of indicators linked with them by workshop participants

Policy	Policy scale	Policy mechanism	Policy topic	Number of indicators linked to it
Open Space Strategies – consultation*	Local	Steering strategy	Socio-economic	17
Active Scotland Delivery Plan	National	Steering strategy	Health	13
Climate Ready Scotland: climate change adaptation programme 2019-2024	National	Steering strategy	Climate change	11
National Planning Framework 4 (NPF4)	National	Steering strategy	Socio-economic	9
National Transport Strategy 2	National	Steering strategy	Transport	8
Water Framework Directive	International	Primary legislation	Environment	7
Local Biodiversity Action Plan (LBAP)	Local	Steering strategy	Environment	7
Mobility strategy	Local	Steering strategy	Transport	7
Biodiversity strategy to 2045	National	Steering strategy	Environment	7
A Scotland where everybody thrives: Public Health Scotland's strategic plan 2022 to 2025	National	Steering strategy	Health	7

* This policy covers several policy topics, socio-economic was chosen as the primary topic as many of the aspects this policy covers fall within this.

The 10 indicators most connected to policies are visible in Table 11. Indicators from all Four Capital categories are represented. There are four people indicators, three environment indicators, two business indicators and one community indicator. The people category indicators were most linked to policies, with the top three indicators coming from this category, followed by the environment. This suggests that the connection of green and blue spaces to people is particularly important in policy. This is perhaps unsurprising as we're exploring the quality of indicators for human use. Additionally, the people and environment categories of indicators were by far the largest categories. Therefore, it is interesting to see that indicators across all four categories are present in Table 11. Overall, the table illustrates that green and blue space quality is relevant across a broad range of policy sectors.

Table 11 Indicators by the number of policies they were linked by workshop participants

Indicator	Indicator category	Number of policies it is linked to
Accessibility – generic	People	9
Mental wellbeing	People	8
SIMD	People	6
Carbon storage	Environment	6
Biodiversity – generic	Environment	5
Renewable energy	Business	5
Financial benefits	Business	5

Education learning	People	4
Children's play	Community	4
Air pollution	Environment	4

The indicator category is represented by the colour: Environmental, People, Community, Business.

3.6 Objective five: Identify barriers to measuring quality indicators and to embedding quality indicators in policy

The workshops explored the barriers to measuring quality indicators and to embedding the indicators into policy.

3.6.1 Barriers to measuring quality indicators

Two barriers were identified that were specific to measuring quality indicators. These included:

3.6.1.1 Complex methods

The evolving nature of technologies and methods used over time was identified as reducing the consistency of measurement. Similarly, the evolving and unpredictable nature of the climate and biodiversity crises adds to this complexity.

Workshop participants also discussed the important role that citizen science could play to assist with measuring quality indicators, particularly as this allows for larger areas of data collection. However, they identified significant challenges of facilitating citizen science, due to the training required to ensure consistency and accuracy of results.

On a broader, societal level, participants discussed the negative impact of capitalism and short-sighted projects with immediate impacts that were favoured over long-term perspectives. This meant that quality indicators that focused more on long-term factors could be left out of methodological approaches.

3.6.1.2 Poorly defined indicators

The indicators themselves were discussed as providing barriers to measuring them. This was particularly the case if they were subjective and could be presented or interpreted in multiple ways in different policy documents.

Moreover, the use of proxies was discussed as potentially problematic, as stakeholders can get focused on the indicator, rather than what it is a proxy for. Moreover, the suitability of the proxy may change over time as the context changes.

Participants also raised that indicators could have competing outcomes, which could prevent them from being used simultaneously.

3.6.2 Barriers to embedding indicators into policy

There were three barriers identified by the workshop participants that were specific to embedding indicators into policy, including the following:

3.6.2.1 Public perception

If there was no or little public support for the indicators it can act as barrier to them entering policy, particularly as policymakers were discussed as being risk averse in their approach to determining policy.

3.6.2.2 Policy cycle

Participants discussed the several stages of policy development for both national and local level policy. This was referred to as the policy cycle. To fit the quality indicators into the policy cycle, and therefore embed them into policy, the workshop participants suggested that there needed to be appropriate evidence for immediate benefits and outcomes of the indicators. This would enable policymakers to feel confident that the policy would translate into on-the-ground action. This aligns with observations about the risk averse nature of policymakers discussed above, as well as the potential for short termism raised in the *complex methods* section.

Participants also indicated that policymakers' focus on the policy cycle could lead them to lose sight of the purpose of quality indicators, preventing them from being included in policy.

3.6.2.3 Policy coherence

Participants highlighted how incoherence within policy can act as a barrier to embedding quality indicators into policy. For example, if there is the possibility of competing or conflicting policy objectives and the priority of the economy; or when indicators themselves may have competing objectives, as mentioned in the *poorly defined indicators* section above.

Moreover, if there was not the appropriate legislation to enable the indicators to be part of policy, such as legislation that would require policies to include indicators, this can also prevent indicators being part of policies.

3.6.3 Crosscutting barriers

Two identified barriers were common to both these aspects of implementation.

3.6.3.1 Personnel knowledge, skills and capacity

Participants highlighted that those responsible for measuring quality may not have adequate training to do this. Similarly, those responsible for determining policy also may not have the appropriate knowledge to do this. This lack of knowledge was often connected to limited resources both in terms of time and money of the people and organisations involved.

Additionally, the siloed nature of working was discussed as frequently preventing stakeholders from developing broader, holistic knowledge, and skills.

3.6.3.2 Availability, accuracy, and scale of data

Workshop participants indicated that the availability, accuracy, and scale of data can be a barrier to the effective use of quality indicators on the ground and in policy. For the quality indicators to be effective, the appropriate data are needed.

3.7 Objective six: Identify potential impacts of the indicators

The workshops focused on the impact of improving quality indicators on three different key areas: wider society, the work of the participants, and the green and blue spaces. The impacts identified are summarised in Table 12. Further detail can be found in Appendix J. The impacts of improving quality indicators are important for policymakers as there was a suggestion from the workshops that if we improve these quality indicators, those responsible for managing these green and blue spaces will know better what works to improve the quality of these green and blue spaces. If we can improve the quality of green and blue spaces, participants suggested people will care more about them and it will create a reinforcing positive cycle, with all the benefits outlined below.

Table 12 Impacts of improved quality indicators

Impact focus	Improved quality indicators lead to improved...
<i>Wider society</i>	Quality of outdoor space <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More opportunities for outside time including for learning and education. - More engaged society. - Greater value placed on quality space by society.
	Community resilience and empowerment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resilience to natural disasters. - More community control over green and blue spaces. - Increased equality as more consistency of quality green and blue spaces across different areas.
	Health and wellbeing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spending more time outdoors. - Increased physical activity. - Improved air quality, noise levels and temperature. - Improved food and ecosystem services.
	Local economies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job creation through more businesses and activities within the green and blue spaces. - Increase in local housing prices. - Better value for money, as green and blue spaces still free to be in.
<i>Work of the participants</i>	Monitoring of green and blue spaces <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved consistency throughout Scotland – same training used nationally. - Improved quality of data collected, making it easier to analyse and spot trends.
	Targeted interventions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connected to better monitoring and evidenced based decision making. - More effective resource prioritisation.
	Engagement with wider public <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved monitoring leads to better reporting to the wider public. - Increases knowledge and trust of wider public. - Increases likelihood of involvement in citizen science projects.
<i>Green and blue spaces</i>	Monitoring and consistency across spaces <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More targeted interventions. - Improved pathways for connectivity for people and nature.
	Ecology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved biodiversity, nature connectivity, and distinctiveness. - Improved ecosystem services. - Improved climate resilience and adaptation.

Many of the impacts identified in Table 12 may have several other knock-on impacts not identified here and may also have both positive and negative aspects to them. However, the impacts give a sense as to the importance of quality green and blue space not just environmentally, but also to social, community, economy, and health and wellbeing considerations as well.

4. Limitations

Throughout this body of work, we have only considered publicly accessible blue and green spaces, excluding grey spaces (e.g., town squares with only concrete surface). While this is a specific choice to focus on more natural areas, this will limit the applicability of our findings for use within Open Space Strategies (Scottish Government, 2019). Within these strategies Local Authorities must include blue, green, and grey outdoors spaces, and therefore consider management at a wider scale than we present here.

Although we attempted to target a wide range of stakeholders, both the survey participants and workshop participants were biased towards national and local level policy, with little representation from businesses. This dominance of policy stakeholders likely reflects the interest of policymakers in managing green and blue spaces as a whole. In contrast, businesses will more likely interact with specific spaces relevant to their business, and therefore have less interest in research on green and blue space in general. It may also relate to the time commitment for the workshops, in particular, and further research may wish to target businesses using more flexible methods (e.g. one-to-one interviews).

Both the surveys and workshops had some representation from islands, but this was, unsurprisingly given the comparatively small population size, less than that of organisations from mainland Scotland. Given the specific challenges of working on islands, and their unique environments, it is likely that measurement of quality would vary in these locations and application of our results to islands should be done with care.

In general, we present an average result across Scotland, each individual green and blue space may vary in their qualities and needs from local users. The results from our work should therefore be used as a starting point for measuring of quality, with flexibility applied to allow for the local characters of Scotland's green and blue spaces to be maintained.

There has been recent work carried out to create a biodiversity metric for use in Scotland (McVittie et al., 2023). This work was published in September 2023, and so was not able to be incorporated into the workshop discussion, however it will be considered in this work taken forward.

4.1 Survey limitations

Although the survey had some representation from all publicly accessible green and blue space types, parks and gardens were dominant. Limited representation was seen from burial grounds, sports areas, crop land, and marsh and transitional waters. These underrepresented areas are all sites with highly specific uses, and we suggest that further focused work on these areas would be valuable. The sample size of the survey is likely not representative of all green and blue space

stakeholders, and so further investigation of other users types, particularly business, may be beneficial.

4.2 Workshop limitations

The workshop had limitations with reference to the attendees and the content of the workshop.

There was a difference in numbers of attendees at the two workshops (14 for Perth and five for Aberdeen), leading to different experiences of the workshops and possibly more time for those at the Aberdeen workshop to discuss and reflect. While this potentially led to the activities developing in slightly different ways in the two workshops, the results were still treated the same and amalgamated for the report.

During the workshop, it was not always possible to reach a consensus amongst participants due to time constraints for some of the activities. This led to activities, such as Activity 1 not producing the desired outcomes; this lack of consensus was, however, a finding in itself.

5. Conclusions

The conclusions from the research are separated for each objective. The first paragraph provides the key take aways for Scottish Government from this objective, the remainder provides a more detailed conclusion of the results.

5.1 Objective one: Identify any indicators missing from the literature review, either in current use or aspirational

An extensive list of green and blue space quality indicators, organised by environment, people, community, business categories, is now available. This will assist policymakers and green and blue space managers to know available options for measuring the quality of green and blue spaces.

Sixty-eight indicators were identified through the literature review. An additional 4 were identified through the survey which consisted of 40 useable entries, mainly from local level policymakers, covering a variety of different types of green and blue spaces. These 72 indicators were taken to the workshops to explore further their importance, how the indicators might (or might not) work together, their connection to policy, the barriers to their use, and their possible impact. The indicators were organised into four categories, based on the “Four Capitals” approach. This approach provides a lens through which to conceptualise the benefits of publicly available green and blue spaces, and has been applied by the Scottish Government in relation to post-Covid recovery (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020).

5.2 Objective two: Categorise quality indicators according to importance, including consideration of green and blue space types and for whom

Information on the importance rankings of each indicator, provided by participants of the survey and workshops, is now available. “Importance” was defined here as importance for the indicator’s role in the green and blue spaces which the participant is involved in. Similar to objective one, the indicators are organised by environment, people, community, business categories, so that policymakers and green and blue space managers can identify the important and most important

indicators in each category according to their needs. These needs may vary depending on the green or blue space(s) they are managing.

19 indicators were ranked as most important in either both green and blue spaces, or in one of these types of spaces. All the indicators in the most important category were either environment or people category indicators, with the majority being environmental indicators. However, it is worth remembering that the environment and people category indicators combined account for 83% of the 72 indicators identified.

5.3 Objective three: Understand bundles or trade-offs between quality indicators, as well as between green and blue space quality

The report has identified where indicators work together and where there may be trade-offs and clearly set these out. This means that policymakers and green and blue space managers can use this information to see what possible trade-offs with other indicators might be present if they used a certain quality indicator, or, alternatively, what might also be connected to a quality indicator they are using, through seeing the bundles it may be part of.

Bundles and trade-offs identified both positive and negative relationships between indicators of green and blue space quality. There were a number of indicators that fed into multiple bundles, which may be more valuable to measure if resources are limited.

5.4 Objective four: Identify the policies to which quality indicators may be relevant, and how or where they may impact

The report illustrates how green and blue space quality indicators are relevant for an array of policy sectors and scales, particularly social policy sectors (socio-economic, health, transport). This reiterates that publicly available green and blue space quality has a wide-reaching impact, as is identified through objective six. Additionally, whilst all categories of indicators were highly connected to policy, indicators within the people category were the most connected with policy. This is in contrast to the majority of indicators considered as most important ranked, identified through objective two, which were in the environment category.

The policies identified through this workshop activity were not viewed as an exhaustive list of Policies relevant to quality indicators, rather they were used to get a sense of the range of policies that might be relevant. In total 91 policies were identified in the workshop. These policies covered a range of scales (International, UK, Scotland, Local Authority) and a range of policy types (steering strategies, instruments, primary legislations). Most of the quality indicators (62 out of 72) were connected with one or more of the identified policies. Not all the policies had indicators connected to them.

5.5 Objective five: Identify barriers to measuring quality indicators and to embedding quality indicators in policy

The possible barriers to measuring quality indicators and using them in policy were identified. This enables policymakers and green and blue spaces managers to see where further work might be needed to use these indicators successfully.

There appear to be three types of barriers identified by the workshop participants. These are:

- Barriers to those using the indicators: around knowledge, capacity, skills, methods, data.
- Barriers within policy: fitting into the policy cycle and coming up against policy incoherence.
- Barriers to external perceptions of the quality indicators: public misunderstanding quality indicators making it harder for them to value or to be used in any citizen science initiatives.

5.6 Objective six: Identify potential impacts of the indicators

The findings illustrate that workshop participants believe that improving green and blue space quality indicators through increased knowledge and a shared understanding of the indicators (produced through this research) will better facilitate understanding of what helps to improve green and blue spaces. This will have a wide range of impacts that touch on many aspects of society, not just the environment. This strengthens the case for investing in green and blue space quality indicators.

Improved quality indicators make the work of those managing green and blue spaces easier by giving them a standardised tool kit, enabling a shared understanding of quality across green and blue spaces. A standardised way to measure quality will help green and blue space managers to understand what works to improve the quality of their spaces. This better allows for the improvement of green and blue space quality, which enables more people to get out, enjoy and engage with their green and blue spaces more. This has a host of well reported benefits for those people.

5.7 Next steps

This work forms part of a work package within the JHI-C6-1 project titled *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing*. We will determine which indicators identified here to prioritise and take forward to create a validated toolkit for estimating the costs and benefits of green and blue space management, accounting for specific underrepresented groups. In the final two years of the project this toolkit will be applied to rural and urban case studies to assess its on-the-ground usability. This starts to address the possible need for place-based indicators. However, further work would be needed to explore the use of place-based indicators in more detail.

5.8 Funding

The JHI-C6-1 project titled *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* is funded by the Scottish Government under the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Quality indicator codebook

Indicator	Description
Environment	
Green/blue space area	Reference to the size of the green or blue space
Biodiversity – generic	Reference to biodiversity
Biodiversity – species richness	Reference to number of species
Biodiversity – species abundance	Reference to number of individuals of species
Biodiversity – species diversity	Reference to number of species relative to number of individuals
Vegetation cover	Reference to vegetation, or plant cover
NDVI	Any reference to NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
Size and number of trees	Reference to tree size and number
Protected area	Reference to any protected area
Protected plants/animals	Reference to any protected plant, or animal, also key species
Ecological connectivity (inc. edge diversity index)	How ecologically connected different areas studied were, often just referred to as ecological connectivity, or related to edge diversity, mean patch size and connectivity, functionality as an ecological corridor, unfragmented open space
Physical Structure	Reference to physical structure (e.g. forest structure, terrain structure)
Diversity of terrain	Any reference to diversity of terrain or topographic diversity
Pollination potential	The amount of pollination and seed dispersal possible in an area
Water quality – generic	Reference to water quality
Water quality – disease causing bacteria	Reference to measuring human disease potential of water, e.g. presence of E-coli or faecal indicator bacteria
Water quality - nutrient	Reference to measuring the presence of nutrients in water, such as nitrates, phosphorous, ammonia etc.
Water flow & discharge	Reference to the flow or discharge of water
Regulation of ecological quality	Where there is discussion of regulating certain ecological functions
Soil conservation	Soil quality and conservation referred to
Temperature	Any reference to temperature, land, soil, air, water etc.
Noise pollution	Excessive noise load
Air pollution	Air pollution, PM10 and NO2 etc
Allergenic potential	The potential to add to allergies (only came up once)
Presence of wildlife	Whether there is any wildlife present (animal only)
Presence of water	Reference to whether there is water present in the greenspace
Hemeroby/ naturalness	Reference to naturalness or the hemeroby index (an index of naturalness/human interference), genuineness of the landscape

Integration with landscape	Any reference to the area surrounding the green or blue space e.g. integration with local landscape or proportion of surrounding 200m that is green etc.
Carbon storage	Amount of carbon stored in green or blue space per year or reference to carbon sequestration
Drought susceptibility	Reference to whether the area suffers often from drought
People	
Duration of time spent in G/BS	Reference to duration spent in green or blue space
Frequency of visits to G/BS	Reference to the frequency of visits to green or blue space
Accessibility – generic	Reference to general accessibility
Accessibility – internal	Accessibility within the green or blue space, such as paths
Accessibility – getting there	Accessibility to the green or blue space, e.g., public transport, cycle lanes
Accessibility – proximity	How close green or blue space was to people
Accessibility – barriers	Whether there were any barriers to access
Accessibility – for those with a disability	Whether there was any provision for disabled access
Aesthetics – generic	Reference to aesthetics generally
Aesthetics – maintenance, well kept, management, cleanliness	Mention of green or blue space maintenance and management, cleanliness and whether well kept
Aesthetics – view	Mention of the view with reference to aesthetics
Aesthetics – vegetation	Mention to the vegetation with reference to the aesthetics of the green or blue space
Incivilities	Reference to graffiti, vandalism, dog fouling, litter. Similar to cleanliness but negative
Uniqueness	Rareness or distinctiveness of the landscape
Safety	Reference to safety and security of the area
Services – generic	Services in general
Services – people	These are the non-recreational services that enable people to use the space
activities	Activities in general (i.e. no specific reference to activities carried out)
Education/Learning potential	If there were spaces or potential for learning present – often focused on children, but not always
Physical health	Reference to physical health and physical health improvement
Physical activity	Reference to physical activity
Recreation – recreation facilities	Reference to recreation facilities or spaces for recreation
Recreations – Sports facilities	Reference to sports facilities, such as tennis court or sports pitches etc.,
Mental wellbeing	Reference to mental health or wellbeing
Spiritual wellbeing	Reference to feeling calm, tranquil, at peace etc.,
Connection to nature	Reference to any form of connection to nature

Quietness	Reference to quietness of an area – not feelings of quietness – that is spiritual wellbeing
Indexes of multiple deprivation	Reference to SIMD or IMD
Food growing opportunities	Including community orchards, edible hedges, community gardens, allotments, raised beds etc
Invasive species	Reference to the presence of native or non-native invasive species
Community	
Services – community	Reference to services, which are viewed as specific objects (e.g. picnic tables) or spaces (e.g. meeting spaces), that enable the community to gather
Children's play	Where children's play or a playground is explicitly discussed.
Cultural	Reference to anything cultural, such as open-air theatres, art etc.,
Historical	Reference to anything historical, such as historical monuments
Spiritual	Reference to anything spiritual or religious
Social interaction	Mention of connecting to people, or social interaction/relations/inclusion, not linked to a specific place or object (as this is covered by services – community)
Business	
Services – business	Reference to services that are important for/are a business, such as cafes
Tourism potential	Where the possible impact of tourism is directly referred to
Financial benefits	Reference to some form of possible financial gain
Flood risk	Any reference to flood risk, flood damage, flood modelling
house price	Reference to house prices, house sales, or property/land value
Renewable energy generation	Reference to the presence of actual or potential renewable energy generation e.g., ground source heat, water source heat, micro-hydro

Appendix B – Concept map matrices for green and blue space respectively
See additional files of these tables for easier viewing

Appendix C – Green and blue space concept map value differences and solutions

Table: Green Space concept map value differences and solutions:

Indicator relationships	Perth Value	Aberdeen Value	Chosen Value	Reasoning
Size and number of trees -> Presence of wildlife		1, -1	Removed from analysis	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Size and number of trees -> duration of time spent in Green/Blue space		1, -1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Children's play -> safety	1	-1	1	Effort to increase accessibility, lighting, etc. would likely make the area safer, not less safe.
Presence of wildlife -> Size and number of trees		1, -1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Duration of time spent in green/blue space -> Size and number of trees		1, -1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Frequency of visits to green/blue space -> Size and number of trees		1, -1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Flood risk -> Soil conservation	-1	1	-1	Increased flood risk reduces the measure of soil being conserved, therefore negative relationship.
Flood risk -> drought susceptibility	-1	1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Size and number of trees -> Frequency of visits to green/blue space		1, -1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Regulation of ecological quality -> Invasive species	1	-1	-1	As regulations increase invasive species populations decrease, so negative relationship.
Drought susceptibility -> Flood risk	-1	1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.

Table: Blue space concept map value differences and solutions

Indicator relationships	Perth Value	Aberdeen Value	Chosen Value	Reasoning
Water quality – Disease causing bacteria -> Safety	1, -1	-1	-1	Increase in levels of Water quality – Disease causing bacteria would have negative impact on safety.

Frequency of visits to green/blue space -> Safety	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Renewable energy generation -> Green/blue space area	1, -1		-1	Unclear how this could be a positive relationship (i.e., how an increase in Renewable energy generation could increase Blue space area).
Index of multiple deprivation -> Education/learning potential	0.5, -0.5		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Safety -> Water quality – Disease causing bacteria	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Safety -> Frequency of visits to green/blue space	1, -1		1	If there is an increase in safety there is likely to be an increase in frequency of visits, so positive relationship.
Biodiversity – generic -> Frequency of visits to green/blue space	1	-1	Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Mental wellbeing -> Frequency of visits to green/blue space	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Diversity of terrain -> Uniqueness	-1	1	1	An increase in Diversity of terrain would lead to an increase in Uniqueness, so positive relationship.
Water quality generic -> Physical health	-1	1	1	An increase in water quality would lead to an increase in Physical health, so positive relationship.
Education/learning potential -> Index of multiple deprivation	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Frequency of visits to green/blue space -> Mental wellbeing	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Physical health -> Index of multiple deprivation	1, -1		Removed from analysis.	Value of relationship can be both positive and negative.
Green/blue space area -> Renewable energy generation	1, -1		1	An increase in area means more potential for Renewable energy generation, so positive relationship.

Appendix D – Additional indicators

Table illustrating additional indicators identified by participants

Additional indicator	Existing indicator to which it relates
Accessibility in all weathers	
All weather options	Accessibility - generic
Access to toilet facilities	
Path quality e.g., how we improve accessibility	Accessibility - internal
Effective maintenance over time	Aesthetics - maintenance
Community group activity	
Social cohesion	Social interaction
Play - different types of play opportunity e.g., physical, creative, social	Children's playspaces
Health & Wellbeing	Mental wellbeing/physical health
Permeability of the landscape matrix i.e., how easily species can move through the landscape	
Connectivity to other green / blue spaces	Ecological connectivity
Biodiversity	Biodiversity – generic
Canopy cover	Vegetation cover/size and number of trees
Economic	Services - business
Natural surveillance - areas overlooked by housing etc	Safety
New Indicators	
Food growing opportunities (community orchards, edible hedges, community gardens, allotments, raised beds etc)	
Drought susceptibility	
Invasive species (non-native)/Invasive species (native)	
Renewable energy generation (actual/potential) e.g., ground source heat, water source heat, micro-hydro)	
Excluded indicators	
Engagement level (for participants)	Not clear what would be measured
Citizen science undertaken	Not considered quality of the space itself
Environment	Too vague, encompasses many other indicators
Sustainability level	Too vague
Habitats created for wildlife e.g., bug hotels	Not considered quality of the space itself

Appendix E – Variation in Indicator Ranking

Table illustrating the indicators with multiple rankings identified from the workshop

Indicator	Ranking(s) for green space	Ranking(s) for blue space
Flood risk	Important	Most important
Safety	Least important	Important
Integration with landscape	Most important and Least important	Important
Pollination potential	Most important	Important
Indexes of multiple deprivation in which the site sits	Most important and Least important	Important
Physical health	Most important	Important
Accessibility generic	Most important	Important
Biodiversity – generic	Most important and Least important	Least important
Presence of wildlife	Most important	Important
Protected status of the green/blue space	Most important	Important
Social interaction	Most important and Least important	Important
Carbon storage	Most important and Least important	Most important
Aesthetics – Maintenance (e.g., clean facilities)	Most important and Least important	Most important
Food growing opportunities	Least important, Important, and Most important	Least important and Important
Drought susceptibility	Least important and Important	Important and Most important
Invasive species	Least important and Important	Most important
Renewable energy generation	Least important, Important, and Most important	Least important, Important, and Most important

Appendix F – Green Space Concept Map – Aberdeen Workshop *Please zoom for details.*

Appendix H – Green Space Concept Map – Perth Workshop. *Please zoom for details.*

Appendix I – Blue Space Concept Map – Perth Workshop. *Please zoom for details.*

Appendix J – Detailed description of the impacts of improving quality indicators on the wider society, the work of the workshop participants, and green and blue spaces.

The first impact area discussed was the impact for the **wider society**. Workshop participants came up with the following themes:

Improvements to quality of outdoor space.

Improvements to quality of outdoor space was a broad wider society impact discussed by the workshop participants. Specifically, participants mentioned how improving quality indicators would enable more opportunities for outside time, including for learning and education. A knock-on impact of greater learning opportunities mentioned was a more informed and engaged society. Participants also suggested that there would be greater value put on quality space by society, act as a reinforcing circle, as society would value quality space more and take better care of their green and blue spaces.

Improvements for communities

Participants highlighted how improving quality indicators would lead to improved community resilience, particularly for disaster management, as they would have better quality green and blue spaces that were themselves more resilient. They also discussed how improved quality indicators could lead to communities to feel a greater sense of control and agency over their green and blue spaces leading to community empowerment. Moreover, participants raised how improved quality indicators could lead to improved equality, as it would make the quality of green and blue spaces in an area more consistent and it could lead to better transparency, as there was greater consistency among the quality indicators, making them easier to understand.

Improvements for health and wellbeing

The workshop participants indicated that an improvement in quality indicators would lead to a general improvement to public health and wellbeing due to a variety of factors, such as spending more time outdoors and likely connected increased physical activity, as well as improved air quality, noise levels, and temperature. They also specifically discussed how improved quality indicators would likely improve food and ecosystem services, which is particularly relevant with a changing climate and also feeds into health and wellbeing improvements.

Economic improvements

Moreover, workshop participants also raised how improvements in quality indicators would likely lead to economic improvements. Specifically, they discussed how it would lead to job creation, through the development of more businesses and activities in the green and blue spaces, not to mention more people required to measure the quality indicators. They discussed that it would lead to improvements to houses in the area, increasing the house prices of those houses. They also highlighted how it would overall lead to better value for money for society as the green and blue spaces would be improved whilst still being free spaces to be in.

The second was the impact of improving quality indicators for **the work of the participants**. The following themes emerged:

Improvements in monitoring

The workshop participants outlined how improving quality indicators would lead to improved monitoring, particularly improved consistence across different areas, with the same training used nationally. This will improve the quality of data collected and make it easier to compare different areas and see trends over time, which will in turn increase understanding on linkages such as nature and health.

Improvements in targeted interventions

The improvement in quality indicators and subsequent improvements in monitoring was also discussed as leading to more efficient and effective working overall, with improved certainty and accuracy likely to lead to better evidenced based decision making and more effective resource prioritisation.

Improved engagement with the wider public

Participants also highlighted how improved data and monitoring could lead to improved reporting, which helps to make results more communicable. This in turn would hopefully lead to a more engaged wider public and more opportunities to increase citizen science.

The third was the impact on improving quality indicators **for green and blue space**. The participants discussed the following themes:

Improved monitoring

Similar to the improvements for participants' work, participants also raised how improved monitoring would be an impact for the green and blue spaces, as it would enable more targeted interventions and a deeper understanding on how these spaces were improving from these, creating a positive, reinforcing cycle. Moreover, and again similar to the impacts on the participants' work, participants highlighted how this could lead to better pathways for connectivity for people and nature, opening up further connections with other initiatives not currently working with or in green or blue spaces.

Improved ecology

By far the largest impact for green and blue spaces discussed by workshop participants was improved ecology of these areas. Participants suggested there would be improved biodiversity, nature connectivity, and distinctiveness. There was also a focus on the improved ecosystem services from improving the quality indicators, with participants raising the possibility of improved climate resilience and adaptation, including increased carbon storage and tree cover.